

THE INTERFACE CRACK-TIP FIELD BETWEEN ELASTIC AND VISCOELASTIC MATERIAL IN AN INFINITE LENGTH STRIP

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SUMMARY: The dynamic stress intensity factor has been studied about the Griffith crack between elastic and viscoelastic layers in an infinite length strip under mode I impact load. The controlling equations are deduced after Laplace and Fourier integral transforms of the basic equations. The analytical expressions of displacement and stress in Laplace domain are obtained by inverse Fourier integral transform, the constitutive and geometrical equations. By defining dislocation density function, the Cauchy singular integral equations are obtained according to the boundary conditions and the problem is reduced to algebraic equations; then it can be solved with the method of collocation dots in Laplace domain. The time response of dynamic stress intensity factor is calculated with the numerical method and the result shows that the influence of shear relaxation parameter on mode I dynamic stress intensity factor is bigger than mode II, and the influence of swelling relaxation parameter is the opposite.

KEYWORDS: viscoelasticity, infinite length strip, interface crack, impact load, Laplace and Fourier integral transforms, dynamic stress intensity factor, dislocation density function, singular integral equation.

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that bi-material structure has broad application in engineering, which promotes the development of interface fracture mechanics. Interface play a significant role in determining the strength and toughness of many advanced composite and structural systems, and interface cracks induced by the mismatch of materials mechanical properties do not only reduce the load carrying capacity in the engineering structure made by layered composite, but also be the reason for delamination failures. Further, the strength of the structural components of different materials welded together is governed only by the interfaces behaviours, and may be weakened by the development of cracks along the bonding. Therefore, it is of practical importance to assess the stress field near the interface cracks.

The dynamic response of interface cracks between two dissimilar elastic materials has been studied widely. Kundu [1] studied the dynamic SIF of interface crack under impact loading with the method based on Betti's reciprocal theorem. Li [2] investigated the dynamic SIF of one Griffith interface crack in a four-layered composite by reducing the mixed boundary problem to the Cauchy-type singular integral equation. As for interface crack between two dissimilar orthotropic or anisotropic materials, Wang [3] extended the investigation to

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modified Griffith interface cracks that has contact region at the crack-tip. The dynamic response between two dissimilar viscoelastic materials also has been studied. Georgiadis [4] researched on the dynamic SIF of Griffith crack, penny-shaped crack and half-infinite crack in homogenous viscoelastic material under impact loading. Wei Pei-jun [5] depicted the dynamic response of interface cracks between two dissimilar viscoelastic materials. Tang Li-qiang [6-8] analyzed the asymptotic field of dynamic growing crack along a rigid/viscoelastic and quasi-static growing crack along elastic/ viscoelastic bi-material interface. It is noted that while elastic analyses of interfacial crack problems have covered both static and dynamic cases, elastic-viscoelastic analyses so far are mostly limited to stationary and quasi-statically cases. The objective of the present paper is to investigate the dynamic response of an interface crack between elastic and viscoelastic materials under mode I impact loading.

DEDUCTION OF THE SINGULAR INTEGRAL EQUATIONS

It is considered in the present paper that dynamic response of the Griffith cracks of length $2a$ between elastic and viscoelastic material in an infinite length strip. The strip has a finite width $2h$ in the y direction; it is of infinite extent in the x direction as shown in Fig. 1. At $t=0$, the mode I impact loading act on the crack faces, $s_{yy} = p_0H(t)$, $H(t)$ is the unit step-function.

The Solution of Viscoelastic Material in Laplace Domain

The constitutive equation of viscoelastic material are expressed as

$$s_{ij}(x,t) = \int_0^t G_{ijkl}(x,t-t) \frac{\mathcal{Q} e_{kl}(x,t)}{\mathcal{Q} t} dt \quad (1)$$

The Laplace integral transforms of it for isotropic media is

$$s_{ij}^* = PG_1^* e_{ij}^* + P e_{kk}^* d_{ij}^* (G_2^* - G_1^*)/3 \quad (2)$$

Where G_1, G_2 are independent relaxing functions.

The geometry equation under small deformation and the moving equation respectively are

$$e_{ij} = (u_{i,j} + u_{j,i})/2 \quad (3)$$

$$s_{ij,j} = r_{i0} \quad (4)$$

The governing equations expressed by displacement in Laplace and Fourier integral transforms domain are derived as

$$\begin{cases} -2(2s^2G_1^* + s^2G_2^* + 3rP)\bar{u}_x^* + (2G_2^* + G_1^*)is \frac{\mathcal{Q}\bar{u}_y^*}{\mathcal{Q}y} + 3G_1^* \frac{\mathcal{Q}^2\bar{u}_x^*}{\mathcal{Q}y^2} = 0 \\ -3(s^2G_1^* + 2rP)\bar{u}_y^* + (2G_2^* + G_1^*)is \frac{\mathcal{Q}\bar{u}_x^*}{\mathcal{Q}y} + 2(G_2^* + 2G_1^*) \frac{\mathcal{Q}^2\bar{u}_y^*}{\mathcal{Q}y^2} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The solution of governing equations are defined as

$$\bar{u}_x^*(y,P,s) = \int_1^4 m_j F_j(P,s) e^{n_j y}, \quad \bar{u}_y^*(y,P,s) = \int_1^4 F_j(P,s) e^{n_j y} \quad (6)$$

In which $F_1 \sim F_4$ are unknown function, $n_1 \sim n_4$ are the roots of characteristic equations

$$n_{1,2} = \pm \sqrt{(s^2G_1^* + 2rP)/G_1^*}, \quad n_{3,4} = \pm \sqrt{\frac{s^2(2G_1^* + G_2^*) + 3rP}{2(G_1^* + G_2^*)}} \quad (7)$$

$m_1 \sim m_4$ are the following operators

$$m_{1,2} = \pm i \sqrt{(G_1^* s^2 + 2rP)/(G_1^* s^2)}, \quad m_{3,4} = \pm i \sqrt{\frac{s^2(2G_1^* + G_2^*) + 3rP}{s^2 + 3rP}} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 1 A Griffith crack in an infinite strip

By inverse Fourier integral transform to (6), there are

$$u_x^* = \frac{1}{2p} \dot{\partial}_-^{\forall} \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{j=1}^4 m_j F_j(P, s) e^{n_j y} e^{-isx} ds, \quad u_y^* = \frac{1}{2p} \dot{\partial}_-^{\forall} \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{j=1}^4 F_j(P, s) e^{n_j y} e^{-isx} ds \quad (9)$$

Uniting (9)、(2) and (3), there are

$$\begin{cases} s_{xx}^* = \frac{1}{2p} \dot{\partial}_-^{\forall} \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{j=1}^4 A_j(P, s) F_j(P, s) e^{n_j y} e^{-isx} ds \\ s_{yy}^* = \frac{1}{2p} \dot{\partial}_-^{\forall} \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{j=1}^4 B_j(P, s) F_j(P, s) e^{n_j y} e^{-isx} ds \\ s_{xy}^* = \frac{1}{2p} \dot{\partial}_-^{\forall} \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{j=1}^4 C_j(P, s) F_j(P, s) e^{n_j y} e^{-isx} ds \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

In which $A_j(P, s) = P \left(G_2^* - G_1^* \right) n_j - (2G_1^* + G_2^*) ism_j \frac{\forall}{\mathbb{H}} 3$, $C_j(P, s) = PG_1^* (n_j m_j - is) / 2$,
 $B_j(P, s) = P \left(2G_1^* + G_2^* \right) n_j - (G_2^* - G_1^*) ism_j \frac{\forall}{\mathbb{H}} 3$.

The Solution of Elastic Material in Laplace Domain

The constitutive equation of elastic material is

$$s_{0ij} = 2me_{0ij} + l e_{0kk} d_{ij} \quad (11)$$

By the same method, the displacement and stress of elastic material take the following form

$$u_{0x}^* = \frac{1}{2p} \dot{\partial}_-^{\forall} \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{j=1}^4 m_{0j} F_{0j}(P, s) e^{n_{0j} y} e^{-isx} ds, \quad u_{0y}^* = \frac{1}{2p} \dot{\partial}_-^{\forall} \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{j=1}^4 F_{0j}(P, s) e^{n_{0j} y} e^{-isx} ds \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{cases} s_{0xx}^* = \frac{1}{2p} \dot{\partial}_-^{\forall} \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{j=1}^4 A_{0j}(P, s) F_{0j}(P, s) e^{n_{0j} y} e^{-isx} ds \\ s_{0yy}^* = \frac{1}{2p} \dot{\partial}_-^{\forall} \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{j=1}^4 B_{0j}(P, s) F_{0j}(P, s) e^{n_{0j} y} e^{-isx} ds \\ s_{0xy}^* = \frac{1}{2p} \dot{\partial}_-^{\forall} \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{j=1}^4 C_{0j}(P, s) F_{0j}(P, s) e^{n_{0j} y} e^{-isx} ds \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Where $n_{01} \sim n_{04}$, $m_{01} \sim m_{04}$, $A_{0j}(P, s)$, $B_{0j}(P, s)$ and $C_{0j}(P, s)$ are the following operators

$$\begin{aligned} n_{01,2} &= \pm \sqrt{(s^2 m + r_0 P^2) / m}, \quad n_{03,4} = \pm \sqrt{\frac{\xi^2}{\mathbb{H}} (l + 2m) + r_0 P^2 \frac{\forall}{\mathbb{H}} (l + 2m)} \\ m_{01,2} &= \pm i \sqrt{(n \kappa^2 + r_0 P^2) / (n \kappa^2)}, \quad m_{03,4} = \pm i \sqrt{(l + 2m) s^2 / \frac{\xi^2}{\mathbb{H}} (l + 2m) s^2 + r_0 P^2 \frac{\forall}{\mathbb{H}}} \\ A_{0j}(P, s) &= l n_{0j} - (l + 2m)(is) m_{0j}, \quad B_{0j}(P, s) = (l + 2m) n_{0j} - l (is) m_{0j}, \\ C_{0j}(P, s) &= m (n_{0j} m_{0j} - is) \end{aligned}$$

The Boundary Conditions and Interface Joining Conditions

The boundary condition and interface joining condition are as follows

$$s_{yy} \Big|_{y=h} = 0, \quad s_{0yy} \Big|_{y=-h} = 0, \quad s_{xy} \Big|_{y=h} = 0, \quad s_{0xy} \Big|_{y=-h} = 0 \quad (14-1)$$

$$s_{yy} \Big|_{y=0} = s_{0yy} \Big|_{y=0}, \quad s_{xy} \Big|_{y=0} = s_{0xy} \Big|_{y=0} \quad (14-2)$$

$$u_x(x, +0) \Big|_{|x|>a} = u_{0x}(x, -0) \Big|_{|x|>a}, \quad u_y(x, +0) \Big|_{|x|>a} = u_{0y}(x, -0) \Big|_{|x|>a} \quad (14-3)$$

$$s_{yy}(x, \pm 0) \Big|_{|x|<a} = p_0 H(t), \quad s_{xy}(x, \pm 0) \Big|_{|x|<a} = 0 \quad (14-4)$$

Singular Integral Equations in the Laplace Domain

Two dislocation density function in the Laplace domain are defined as

$$g_1^*(\alpha) = \frac{1}{\alpha x} \left[u_x^*(x, +0) - u_x^*(x, -0) \right], \quad g_2^*(\alpha) = \frac{1}{\alpha x} \left[u_y^*(x, +0) - u_y^*(x, -0) \right] \quad (15)$$

From (15) and boundary condition (14-3), yields

$$\int_0^a g_j(\sigma) d\sigma = 0, \quad j = 1, 2 \quad (16)$$

Employing equation (1)-(6) in appendix and Fourier integral transformation on x in equation (15), it leads to

$$\int_0^{\infty} g_1^*(\sigma) e^{isr} d\sigma = is(f_{11}F_3 + f_{12}F_4), \quad \int_0^{\infty} g_2^*(\sigma) e^{isr} d\sigma = is(f_{21}F_3 + f_{22}F_4) \quad (17)$$

Where f_{11} , f_{12} , f_{21} and f_{22} can be seen in appendix.

Then F_3 , F_4 are expressed by $g_1^*(\sigma)$ and $g_2^*(\sigma)$, and taking into account (1)-(2) in appendix, equation (10) and boundary condition (14-4), singular integral equations in the Laplace domain have the following expression

$$\int_0^a \frac{1}{\pi} \left[A_{11} \frac{g_1^*(\sigma)}{r-x} + A_{12} \frac{g_2^*(\sigma)}{r-x} \right] + k_{11}(x, 0, r)g_1^*(\sigma) + k_{12}(x, 0, r)g_2^*(\sigma) d\sigma = \frac{p_0}{P} \quad (18-1)$$

$$\int_0^a \frac{1}{\pi} \left[A_{21} \frac{g_1^*(\sigma)}{r-x} + A_{22} \frac{g_2^*(\sigma)}{r-x} \right] + k_{21}(x, 0, r)g_1^*(\sigma) + k_{22}(x, 0, r)g_2^*(\sigma) d\sigma = 0 \quad (18-2)$$

In which $k_{ij}(x, 0, r) = \frac{1}{2p} \int_0^{\infty} K_{ij}(x, 0, s) - K_{ij}^*(x, 0, s) e^{is(r-x)} ds, i, j = 1, 2$, when $s \in \mathbb{R}$,

$K_{ij}(x, 0, s) = K_{ij}^*(x, 0, s) = \text{sgn}(s)A_{ij}$, K_{ij} and A_{ij} can be found in appendix.

Since $g_1^*(\sigma)$ and $g_2^*(\sigma)$ is coupling in (18-1) and (18-2), Despite it is mode I loading acting on the surface of crack, the stress state of crack front is complex.

$$c = r/a, \quad r1 = x/a, \quad g_i^*(\sigma) = f_i^*(c), \quad k_{ij}(x, 0, r) = L_{ij}(r1, 0, c), \quad i, j = 1, 2 \quad (19)$$

Applying Equation (19) to Equation (18-1) and (18-2), the dimensionless singular integral equations are written as

$$\int_0^1 \frac{1}{\pi} \left[A_{11} \frac{f_1^*(c)}{c-r1} + A_{12} \frac{f_2^*(c)}{c-r1} \right] + L_{11}(r1, 0, c)f_1^*(c) + L_{12}(r1, 0, c)f_2^*(c) dc = \frac{p_0}{P} \quad (20)$$

$$\int_0^1 \frac{1}{\pi} \left[A_{21} \frac{f_1^*(c)}{c-r1} + A_{22} \frac{f_2^*(c)}{c-r1} \right] + L_{21}(r1, 0, c)f_1^*(c) + L_{22}(r1, 0, c)f_2^*(c) dc = 0$$

The single-valued condition (16) of singular integral equations has the corresponding form

$$\int_0^1 f_j^*(c) dc = 0, \quad j = 1, 2 \quad (21)$$

The equation (20) has clear physical meaning: $f_j^*(c)$ is the dislocation density function of crack, integral kernel corresponds to the basic solution of single dislocation, in which singular part denoting the singular characteristic and non-singular part reflecting the influence of impact, material compounding and structure dimension.

Adopting the numerical solution of the singular integral equations in [9], the unknown function are shown that

$$f_1^*(c) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_n T_n(c) / \sqrt{1-c^2}, \quad f_2^*(c) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n T_n(c) / \sqrt{1-c^2} \quad (22)$$

Where $T_n(c) = \cos(n \arccos(c))$ is the first kind Chebyshev polynomials, $A_n = 0$ and $B_n = 0$ can be determined from equation (21), (22) in conjunction with the orthogonal property [10] of $T_n(c)$, and using the integral property [10] of $T_n(c)$, equation (20) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \dot{\bar{a}}_n i(A_{11}A_n\zeta + A_{12}B_n\zeta)U_{n-1}(r1) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \dot{\bar{a}}_n \int_{-1}^1 \dot{\bar{a}}_n \mathcal{L}_{11}(r1,0,c) + B_n \mathcal{L}_{12}(r1,0,c) \mathcal{H}_n(c) / \sqrt{1-c^2} dc = \frac{P_0}{P} \quad (23) \\ \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \dot{\bar{a}}_n i(A_{21}A_n\zeta + A_{22}B_n\zeta)U_{n-1}(r1) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \dot{\bar{a}}_n \int_{-1}^1 \dot{\bar{a}}_n \mathcal{L}_{21}(r1,0,c) + B_n \mathcal{L}_{22}(r1,0,c) \mathcal{H}_n(c) / \sqrt{1-c^2} dc = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Where $U_{n-1}(r1) = \sin(n \arccos(r1)) / \sqrt{1-(r1)^2}$ is the second kind Chebyshev polynomials, to choose the limited term of it, singular integral equations (23) are solved by the method of collocation dots [11], and applying $A_n\zeta$ and $B_n\zeta$, ($n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, L$) to the equation (22), (19), (17), (10) and (1), (2) in appendix, the stress distribution of the viscoelastic material in the surface of boundary are obtained.

THE NUMERICAL SOLUTION OF DYNAMIC STRESS INTENSITY FACTOR

The general form of the dynamic stress intensity factor in the Laplace domain is given by

$$K_I^* + iK_{II}^* = \lim_{x \rightarrow a} \sqrt{2\alpha - a} \left\{ \dot{\bar{g}}_{yy}^*(x, 0) + is_{xy}^*(x, 0) \right\} \quad (24)$$

Introducing the non-dimensional dynamic stress intensity factor

$$m_I^*(P) = K_I^*(P) / (p_0 \sqrt{pa}), \quad m_{II}^*(P) = K_{II}^*(P) / (p_0 \sqrt{pa}) \quad (25)$$

Applying the numerical method of inverse Laplace integral transforms in [12, 13] to (25), it were expressed as

$$m(t_d) = \left(\frac{e^{ct_d}}{T} \right) \left\{ \frac{\bar{m}(c/t_0)}{2t_0} + \sum_{k=1}^N \left[\text{Re} \left[\bar{m} \left(c + \frac{iK\pi}{T} \right) / t_0 \right] \cos \frac{K\pi t_d}{T} \right] - \sum_{k=1}^N \left[\text{Im} \left[\bar{m} \left(c + \frac{iK\pi}{T} \right) / t_0 \right] \sin \frac{K\pi t_d}{T} \right] \right\} \quad (26)$$

Supposing that shear relaxation function and swelling relaxation function are $G_1(t) = G_{10} e^{-t/t_1} H(t)$, $G_2(t) = G_{20} e^{-t/t_2} H(t)$, where shear relaxation parameter and swelling relaxation parameter respectively are $G_{10} = 1.8 \times 10^9 \text{ Pa}$, $G_{20} = 8.1 \times 10^9 \text{ Pa}$, and the Poisson parameter and density of viscoelastic material are $n = 0.35$, $r = 1.4 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/M}^3$, relaxation time $t_1 = t_2 = 3600 \text{ s}$; the Poisson's ratio, density, shear module and Lamé constant of elastic material respectively are $n = 0.3$, $r_0 = 2.3 \times 10^3 \text{ Kg/M}^3$, $m = 2.5 \times 10^9 \text{ Pa}$ and $l = 3.75 \times 10^9 \text{ Pa}$. The thickness of elastic layer and viscoelastic layer are the same, which is $h = 1 \text{ m}$. The numerical results are given in Figure 2 and 3.

Fig. 2 $m(t_d) - t_d$ curves of K_I in the crack-tip of interface between elasticity and visco-elasticity for different parameters

The mode I dynamic stress intensity factor $m(t_d) - t_d$ curve of interface crack between elastic material and viscoelastic material for various G_{10} and G_{20} are showed in figs. 2 (a) and (b), the curves peak value reduce with the G_{10} decreasing, and over-impact phenomena weaken; the curves peak value reduce distinctly with the G_{20} decreasing, and over-impact phenomena weaken obviously. It illustrates that the influence of shear relaxation parameter G_{10} on dynamic stress intensity factor K_I is smaller than the swelling relaxation parameter G_{20} . The mode I dynamic stress intensity factor $m(t_d) - t_d$ curve of interface crack between elastic material and viscoelastic material are showed for various m and l in figure 2 (c) and (d), the curves peak value reduce with the m decreasing, and over-impact phenomena weaken; the curves peak value reduce distinctly with the l decreasing, and over-impact phenomena weaken. It illustrates that the influence of shear module m on dynamic stress intensity factor K_I is smaller than the Lamé constant l .

Fig. 3 $m(t_d) - t_d$ curves of K_{II} in the crack-tip of interface between elasticity and visco-elasticity for different parameters

The mode II dynamic stress intensity factor $m(t_d) - t_d$ curve of interface crack between elastic material and viscoelastic material for various G_{10} and G_{20} are showed in figure 3 (a) and (b), the curves peak value reduce distinctly with the G_{10} decreasing, and over-impact phenomena weaken; The curves peak value reduce with the G_{20} decreasing, and over-impact phenomena weaken. It illustrates that the influence of shear relaxation parameter G_{10} on dynamic stress intensity factor K_{II} is bigger than the swelling relaxation parameter G_{20} . The mode II dynamic stress intensity factor $m(t_d) - t_d$ curve of interface crack between elastic material and viscoelastic material for various m and l are showed in figure 3 (c) and (d), the curves peak value reduce with the m decreasing, and over-impact phenomena weaken; The curves peak value reduce distinctly with the l decreasing, and over-impact phenomena weaken. It illustrates that the influence of shear module m on dynamic stress intensity factor K_{II} is smaller than the Lamé constant l .

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) The influence of shear relaxation parameter G_{10} on dynamic stress intensity factor K_I is smaller than dynamic stress intensity factor K_{II} .
- (2) The influence of swelling relaxation parameter G_{20} on dynamic stress intensity factor K_I is bigger than dynamic stress intensity factor K_{II} .
- (3) The influence of shear module m on dynamic stress intensity factor K_I and K_{II} is smaller than the Lamé constant l .

By optimize rationally the material parameters; the dynamic stress intensity factor of the structure may be reduced.

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APPENDIX

$$F_1 = (B_2C_3 - B_3C_2)F_3e^{n_3h} + (B_2C_4 - B_4C_2)F_4e^{n_4h} + (B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_1h} \quad (1)$$

$$F_2 = (B_3C_1 - B_1C_3)F_3e^{n_3h} + (B_4C_1 - B_1C_4)F_4e^{n_4h} + (B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_2h} \quad (2)$$

$$F_{01} = (B_{02}C_{03} - B_{03}C_{02})F_{03}e^{-n_{03}h} + (B_{02}C_{04} - B_{04}C_{02})F_{04}e^{-n_{04}h} + (B_{01}C_{02} - B_{02}C_{01})e^{-n_{01}h} \quad (3)$$

$$F_{02} = (B_{03}C_{01} - B_{01}C_{03})F_{03}e^{-n_{03}h} + (B_{04}C_{01} - B_{01}C_{04})F_{04}e^{-n_{04}h} + (B_{01}C_{02} - B_{02}C_{01})e^{-n_{02}h} \quad (4)$$

$$F_{03} = D_{121}F_3 + D_{122}F_4, \quad F_{04} = D_{123}F_3 + D_{124}F_4 \quad (5)$$

In which

$$D_{121} = \frac{D_{24}D_{11} - D_{21}D_{14}}{D_{24}D_{13} - D_{23}D_{14}}, \quad D_{122} = \frac{D_{24}D_{12} - D_{22}D_{14}}{D_{24}D_{13} - D_{23}D_{14}}$$

$$D_{123} = \frac{D_{21}D_{13} - D_{23}D_{11}}{D_{24}D_{13} - D_{23}D_{14}}, \quad D_{124} = \frac{D_{22}D_{13} - D_{23}D_{12}}{D_{24}D_{13} - D_{23}D_{14}}$$

In which

$$D_{11} = \frac{B_1(B_2C_3 - B_3C_2)e^{(n_2+n_3)h} + B_2(B_3C_1 - B_1C_3)e^{(n_1+n_3)h} + B_3(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{(n_1+n_2)h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{(n_1+n_2)h}}$$

$$D_{12} = \frac{B_1(B_2C_4 - B_4C_2)e^{(n_2+n_4)h} + B_2(B_4C_1 - B_1C_4)e^{(n_1+n_4)h} + B_4(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{(n_1+n_2)h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{(n_1+n_2)h}}$$

$$D_{13} = \frac{B_{01}(B_{02}C_{03} - B_{03}C_{02})e^{-(n_{02}+n_{03})h} + B_{02}(B_{03}C_{01} - B_{01}C_{03})e^{-(n_{01}+n_{03})h} + B_{03}(B_{01}C_{02} - B_{02}C_{01})e^{-(n_{01}+n_{02})h}}{(B_{01}C_{02} - B_{02}C_{01})e^{-(n_{01}+n_{02})h}}$$

$$D_{14} = \frac{B_{01}(B_{02}C_{04} - B_{04}C_{02})e^{-(n_{02}+n_{04})h} + B_{02}(B_{04}C_{01} - B_{01}C_{04})e^{-(n_{01}+n_{04})h} + B_{04}(B_{01}C_{02} - B_{02}C_{01})e^{-(n_{01}+n_{02})h}}{(B_{01}C_{02} - B_{02}C_{01})e^{-(n_{01}+n_{02})h}}$$

$$D_{21} = \frac{C_1(B_2C_3 - B_3C_2)e^{(n_2+n_3)h} + C_2(B_3C_1 - B_1C_3)e^{(n_1+n_3)h} + C_3(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{(n_1+n_2)h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{(n_1+n_2)h}}$$

$$D_{22} = \frac{C_1(B_2C_4 - B_4C_2)e^{(n_2+n_4)h} + C_2(B_4C_1 - B_1C_4)e^{(n_1+n_4)h} + C_4(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{(n_1+n_2)h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{(n_1+n_2)h}}$$

$$D_{23} = \frac{C_{01}(B_{02}C_{03} - B_{03}C_{02})e^{-(n_{02}+n_{03})h} + C_{02}(B_{03}C_{01} - B_{01}C_{03})e^{-(n_{01}+n_{03})h} + C_{03}(B_{01}C_{02} - B_{02}C_{01})e^{-(n_{01}+n_{02})h}}{(B_{01}C_{02} - B_{02}C_{01})e^{-(n_{01}+n_{02})h}}$$

$$D_{24} = \frac{C_{01}(B_{02}C_{04} - B_{04}C_{02})e^{-(n_{02}+n_{04})h} + C_{02}(B_{04}C_{01} - B_{01}C_{04})e^{-(n_{01}+n_{04})h} + C_{04}(B_{01}C_{02} - B_{02}C_{01})e^{-(n_{01}+n_{02})h}}{(B_{01}C_{02} - B_{02}C_{01})e^{-(n_{01}+n_{02})h}}$$

$$F_{01} = D_{111}F_3 + D_{112}F_4, \quad F_{02} = D_{113}F_3 + D_{114}F_4 \quad (6)$$

In which

$$D_{111} = \frac{(B_{02}C_{03} - B_{03}C_{02})D_{121}e^{-n_{03}h} + (B_{02}C_{04} - B_{04}C_{02})D_{123}e^{-n_{04}h}}{(B_{01}C_{02} - B_{02}C_{01})e^{-n_{01}h}}$$

$$D_{112} = \frac{(B_{02}C_{03} - B_{03}C_{02})D_{122}e^{-n_{03}h} + (B_{02}C_{04} - B_{04}C_{02})D_{124}e^{-n_{04}h}}{(B_{01}C_{02} - B_{02}C_{01})e^{-n_{01}h}}$$

$$D_{113} = \frac{(B_{03}C_{01} - B_{01}C_{03})D_{121}e^{-n_{03}h} + (B_{04}C_{01} - B_{01}C_{04})D_{123}e^{-n_{04}h}}{(B_{01}C_{02} - B_{02}C_{01})e^{-n_{02}h}}$$

$$D_{114} = \frac{(B_{03}C_{01} - B_{01}C_{03})D_{122}e^{-n_{03}h} + (B_{04}C_{01} - B_{01}C_{04})D_{124}e^{-n_{04}h}}{(B_{01}C_{02} - B_{02}C_{01})e^{-n_{02}h}}$$

$$f_{11} = \frac{m_1(B_2C_3 - B_3C_2)e^{n_3h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_1h}} + \frac{m_2(B_3C_1 - B_1C_3)e^{n_3h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_2h}} + m_3 - m_{01}D_{111} - m_{02}D_{113} - m_{03}D_{121} - m_{04}D_{123} \quad (7)$$

$$f_{12} = \frac{m_1(B_2C_3 - B_3C_2)e^{n_4h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_1h}} + \frac{m_2(B_4C_1 - B_1C_4)e^{n_4h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_2h}} + m_4 - m_{01}D_{112} - m_{02}D_{114} - m_{03}D_{122} - m_{04}D_{124} \quad (8)$$

$$f_{21} = \frac{(B_2C_3 - B_3C_2)e^{n_3h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_1h}} + \frac{(B_3C_1 - B_1C_3)e^{n_3h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_2h}} + 1 - D_{111} - D_{113} - D_{121} - D_{123} \quad (9)$$

$$f_{22} = \frac{(B_2C_3 - B_3C_2)e^{n_4h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_1h}} + \frac{(B_4C_1 - B_1C_4)e^{n_4h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_2h}} + 1 - D_{112} - D_{114} - D_{122} - D_{124} \quad (10)$$

Integral kernels K_{ij} have the following expression

$$\begin{aligned} K_{11}(y,s) &= \frac{(Q_{11}f_{22} - Q_{12}f_{21})}{is(f_{22}f_{11} - f_{21}f_{12})}, K_{12}(y,s) = \frac{(Q_{12}f_{11} - Q_{11}f_{12})}{is(f_{22}f_{11} - f_{21}f_{12})} \\ K_{21}(y,s) &= \frac{(Q_{21}f_{22} - Q_{22}f_{21})}{is(f_{22}f_{11} - f_{21}f_{12})}, K_{22}(y,s) = \frac{(Q_{22}f_{11} - Q_{21}f_{12})}{is(f_{22}f_{11} - f_{21}f_{12})} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

In which

$$Q_{11} = \frac{B_1(B_2C_3 - B_3C_2)e^{n_3h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_1h}}e^{n_1y} + \frac{B_2(B_3C_1 - B_1C_3)e^{n_3h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_2h}}e^{n_2y} + B_3e^{n_3y}$$

$$Q_{12} = \frac{B_1(B_2C_4 - B_4C_2)e^{n_4h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_1h}}e^{n_1y} + \frac{B_2(B_4C_1 - B_1C_4)e^{n_4h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_2h}}e^{n_2y} + B_4e^{n_4y}$$

$$Q_{21} = \frac{C_1(B_2C_3 - B_3C_2)e^{n_3h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_1h}}e^{n_1y} + \frac{C_2(B_3C_1 - B_1C_3)e^{n_3h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_2h}}e^{n_2y} + C_3e^{n_3y}$$

$$Q_{22} = \frac{C_1(B_2C_4 - B_4C_2)e^{n_4h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_1h}}e^{n_1y} + \frac{C_2(B_4C_1 - B_1C_4)e^{n_4h}}{(B_1C_2 - B_2C_1)e^{n_2h}}e^{n_2y} + C_4e^{n_4y}$$

$$A_{11} = \frac{\{6(l+m)(G_2 - G_1)(1 - \sqrt{2G_1 + G_2}) - P(G_1 + 2G_2)\}G_1 + G_2 + (G_2 - G_1)\sqrt{2G_1 + G_2}}{3(l+m)(\sqrt{2G_1 + G_2} - 1) + P(G_1 + 2G_2)(1 + \sqrt{2G_1 + G_2})}P \quad (12)$$

$$A_{12} = \frac{i\{6(l+m)(2G_1 + G_2)(-1 + \sqrt{2G_1 + G_2}) + P(G_1 + 2G_2)\}G_1 + G_2 + (G_2 - G_1)\sqrt{2G_1 + G_2}}{3(l+m)(\sqrt{2G_1 + G_2} - 1) + P(G_1 + 2G_2)(1 + \sqrt{2G_1 + G_2})}P \quad (13)$$

$$A_{21} = \frac{iPG_1(\sqrt{2G_1 + G_2} - 1)\{6(l+m) + P(G_1 + 2G_2)\}}{2(l+m)(-1 + \sqrt{2G_1 + G_2}) + P(G_1 + 2G_2)(1 + \sqrt{2G_1 + G_2})} \quad (14)$$

$$A_{22} = \frac{PG_1(\sqrt{2G_1 + G_2} - 1)\{6(l+m) + P(G_1 + 2G_2)\}}{2(l+m)(-1 + \sqrt{2G_1 + G_2}) + P(G_1 + 2G_2)(1 + \sqrt{2G_1 + G_2})} \quad (15)$$